

**THE ROLE OF SPIRITUAL AND MORAL EDUCATION IN THE
THINKING OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS**

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Annotation: This article provides information on the pedagogical activities of primary school teachers.

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Today, in the rapidly developing world, where special attention is paid to the education of the next generation, all-round mature and talented young people who can contribute to the development of our independent country are becoming the demand of the time. The role and work of primary school teachers in the development of the younger generation as a harmoniously developed person is invaluable. If the student is not active in the learning process, the measures taken will not work. . To do this, the teacher must be spiritual, enlightened, and observant. Because a hard-hearted person who has just entered school is idealized. He observes her every move and tries to imitate her. A spiritual teacher must first control his own actions so that the younger generation can be educated.

Spirituality and morality are important in human perfection. Spirituality is the aspiration of a person to the chosen goals, defined as a value inherent in the mind. Morality is a set of general principles of human behavior towards each other and society. Together, they serve the cause of personal perfection.

The implementation of spiritual and moral education in secondary school should be integrated into the minds of students on the basis of the content of education, extracurricular activities, national values.

Primary school teachers, as the most responsible persons in the spiritual and moral development of students, should pay special attention to the following:

- create a healthy environment in the classroom first;
- create a friendly competition between students;
- Limit telephone, television, computer games, etc. that distract students and interfere with common sense;
- Education of students in the spirit of patriotism;
- encourage diligence in students' thinking;
- organization of extracurricular intellectual activities;
- creation of conditions for the formation of a healthy lifestyle among students as a guarantee of spiritual and moral education;

As a condition for the spiritual and moral upbringing of school students, it is to strengthen the interaction between family and school through a system of activities, individual meetings and parent meetings.

With a sense of responsibility, the classroom teacher should pay special attention to classroom exhibitions. By actively cooperating with the family library, it is desirable to create conditions for children to be realized in the system of cultural values. One of the main tasks of an elementary school teacher is to form a healthy lifestyle as a basis for spiritual and moral education, with a special focus on physical education and sports. At the heart of spiritual and moral education are feelings such as patriotism, freedom, culture of communication, the pursuit of knowledge, creativity and hard work, trust, all of which play a leading role in the ideology of young people.

Bringing up a young generation that meets the requirements of the current situation poses a daunting task for educational institutions. It is important to raise the level of our spiritual and educational activities among the general public in order for the younger generation to become well-rounded, full of potential and strong-willed. As spiritual and moral education and national ideology express the goals of the people, it means that the inculcation of the ideology of national independence in the hearts and minds of our people begins at a young age and is completed over the

years. Therefore, this goal is a key task in the field of education. Because the ideology of independence reflects the real dreams and aspirations of the Uzbek people. As humanity turns the pages of history, it instinctively feels the need to explore spiritual and cultural monuments. Throughout his life, he relies on it, strives, draws conclusions from it and teaches it to the younger generation.

The quality of self-awareness is also important in the spiritual and moral development of the younger generation, and this feeling is rooted in the richness of the primary school teachers, worldview and spiritual world. In this regard, in addition to the materials provided in the textbooks, educators should pay special attention to the analysis of works of art that affect the morale of young people who teach, as well as reading and activities. Any young generation brought up in the spirit of national identity, devotion to the Motherland in the way of spirituality and enlightenment of the people will grow up to be a real person in the future.

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